

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

NEW UZBEKISTAN STRATEGY AND NEW CHANGES AND REFORMS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *this in the article . new uzbekistan strategy and in Uzbekistan new changes and reforms ! about in short maolomot given.*

Words: *Uzbekistan development strategy instead to be increased Society management.*

New Uzbekistan development strategy seven direction consists of reaching marked . This is in vain not . After all, our ancestors seven number happiness and omad generous _ _ intention come true emitting characteristic who knew it as an emblem .

Your permission with , Development strategy within instead to be increased eng ustuvor tasks about in short stop I want to pass .

First , free citizenship community development through nationalist state barpo reach , man value and his legal interests to provide focused wide scale our reforms new step by step rises .

In this regard , nationality , language and from religion solid look , in our country living har a citizen , whole of our people well - being to provide service “ New _ Uzbekistan is a nation and humane state ” idea instead increase separately attention we focus . That's it basically local management bodies places problems hal in role and responsibility more strengthen _ That's it for in the future state functions big part from the center regions carried out .

Society management base joint which is, reform fruit directly aks that neighborhood system khokimiyats with bind in order to har a in the neighborhood governor assistant position current are given . Hokim assistant new the work seats Create and poverty shorten responsible will be . Mahalla raisi esa spiritual-enlightenment work instead raise , family and in the neighborhood healthy environment to form answer gives _

That's it with together , in neighborhoods youth issues with regularly engaged in Youth works of the agency will also be represented .

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From this except khokimiyats _ and neighborhoods financial opportunity expand in order to tuman budget additional sources with provided neighborhood _ separately fund formed .

Next important our task is central offices transformation to do through to citizens service do ixcham and effective management system without creating consists of . That's it for the most first of all , the ministry and offices formed reach and termination layout them _ from each other differentiate standing criteria , composition structure and states to determine oid clear requirements functional will be displayed . That's it basically a kind of direction tasks instead increasing offices optimized .

Central offices regional structures with performance to the process new approaches current obsolete _ _ bureaucratic methods voz night _ Bunda regions socio-economic issues speed with independent hal reach on ministry and offices powers more expanded .

Har a network and territory on acceptance made applications execution on the surface leaders report give system set off is placed .

That's it with together , People receptions literally _ people voice , public thought expression that to the structure cycle for additional legal principles is created .

Exactly at the time cadres selection and in place put to the process new , modern approaches current are given . Staff state service choice based on acceptance they are _ for continuous malaka increase efficiency _ evaluation and position on the climb criteria determined .

From this since har a territory , sphere and network maintenance them citizens rights and legal interests how provided depending on evaluation is given .

That's it attitude with " People state authorities not the state authorities to our people service do it is necessary . " to call additional so I mean , " Leaders only to the state not , first of all , man and to their family legal interests to provide service do it is necessary " . Therefore for har a clerk neighborhood and tuman his life ipidan to the needle know condition _

Our great ancestors as the leader said not to be a burden to the people , but rather to the people load to the shoulder take need _ Which one leader of the period this sharp demand If you do not understand them now our people , too itself accepted _ does not .

new Uzbekistan development strategy instead in increasing people representatives who is a senator and deputies separately important place holds .

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High Assembly activities more improvement , our people pending , New Uzbekistan development accelerate service do legislation concept functional exit and to life application law _ _ creativity activities democratization and their execution to provide focused parliament control strengthen ustuvor importance is given .

In this regard parliament by our country on references with performance condition control is obtained . In places execution idorasi leaders report hearing and his as a result according to them relatively impressive measures see instead is increased .

Advanced democratic countries from experience come out , society and state management system some leaders subjective point of view in the eyes of , simple so in fact , their eyebrows depending on not , on the contrary , robust legal criteria has which was institutions activity through instead increase necessary .

In this regard in front of us standing more a important issue - People deputies local boards and governors powers clear to determine oid legal the basics Create time I think he came .

Citizenship society institutes free activity conduct , state and society under the management of active participation reach for necessary conditions create them _ state by support mechanisms more improvement our attention in the center will be . That's it purpose The public chamber formed reach works accelerated .

The public control , state management and social projects to life application in the process citizenship society institutes participation strengthen doir current tasks instead is increased .

In our country democratic update processes more deepen for word and press freedom of citizens information get and uni distribution , own thought and views free report right provide about important measures to life current being done .

Of course it is openness and transparency conditions performance , own maintenance relatively reported critical ideas right acceptance to do old templates with living some to officials may not like it . But , from that solid look , we are this way state policy eng important directions we know one and uni consistent to be continued we will

That's it purpose current in the legislation state authorities and institutions official individuals by mass information tools maintenance obstacle to do , censor installation , editing staff pressure and pressure transfer , materials and technician tools from them illegal as take put actions happen that for responsibility strengthen in the eye is being held .

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One word with in other words , legitimate activity running all journalist and bloggers henceforth since the law and President protected will be .

Second , justice and law priority - populist state build , man dignity supply eng basic and necessary is a condition .

The past period In Uzbekistan this about big affairs instead increased .

Exactly at the time odil sudlov of the system really independence and openness security , law and order authorities activities improvement , advocacy institutes strengthen , this areas activities digitization on in front of us many tasks stands .

In the future administrative courts activities international templates based on improvement on the surface appropriate measures instead is increased .

Sud private property protected standing , citizen and entrepreneurs rights restore through execution offices law within to work forced do system we can create necessary . This is it society development , first in turn , his economic development service does .

We are our country development , population well - being in providing hal seeker place occupying entrepreneur and owners rights har one - sided protection we do In this regard law violation absolutely the way put not emergency condition.

That's it attitude with private property priority in our laws basic principle as marked . State idorasi information believe mol-mulk buy received of the person right indestructibility provided .